

Information and Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ - The Importance of X Information Part III

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In Part II, we noted that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px) = .5(\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) + i .5 (1/i) (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx))$. We argued that even for $\exp(ipx)$, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ taken separately involve both forwards and backwards motion, i.e. p and $-p$. In this note, we try to argue why this should be the case.

We first note that $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length, defines a specific length L which is required for normalization. We argued that $P(x)$ is a uniform distribution for stationary objects. This implies that if there is p free motion, there should exist p and $-p$ at each x , or $P1(p,x)P1(-p,x) = P(x)$ leading to $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution which does not grow indefinitely. We provided arguments in Part I for the presence of px . In order to have the proper normalization in x , one should use $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$. This, we argue has important consequences because a free particle is not restricted to a length L . If one has L in the picture, this seems to imply some kind of reflection (but not in the manner of an infinite well potential). Thus, we argue that $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ has a curious feature. Given $\exp(ipx)$, a reflected particle would be represented by $\exp(-ipx)$ (± 1) because one may have 3.14 phase shift as a wavelength \hbar/p is composed of a crest and trough. Thus, there are two scenarios for a free particle $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)$. These two physical situations are indistinguishable.

Given the L restriction, one may write: $.5(\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) - i .5 (1/i) (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx))$ which collapses back to $\exp(ipx)$. If one postulated a periodic function for $P1(px)$, but did not know the form of this function, one could use the equation: $P1(px) = .5 (P1(px) + P1(-px)) + i .5 (P1(px) - P1(-px))$

Free Particle and Length Restriction

In Newtonian mechanics, a free particle is described by p and energy. It spends the same amount of time in each dx and one may write $x = vt$, where $v = \text{velocity} = \text{constant}$. If, however, one wishes to describe matters in terms of probability in x , then this probability must be normalized to 1 and this implies a fixed length L which contradicts the notion of free motion at the endpoints, but is required for normalization. Thus:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((1))$$

((1)) describes the arrangement of stationary objects in L and so in this view there is no problem with a constraint of L . If one wishes to consider freely moving objects, then there is an issue. To make them stationary one requires p and $-p$ at each x such that:

$$P1(px)P1(-px) = P(x) \quad \text{or} \quad P1(px) = \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} \quad ((2))$$

Here we combine px as the argument for reasons given in Part I. Thus, the free particle probability $P1$ is constrained by L in ((2)). This seems to have important implications because physically such a constraint would imply reflection. In other words, a particle moving to the right

with $\exp(ipx)$ should be associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ which seems unusual. Furthermore, $\exp(ipx)$ has a wavelength which is \hbar/p and consists of a crest and a trough so the natural unit is half a wavelength, but there is a phase shift of 3.14 equivalent to -1 (a trough is minus a crest) or $\exp(i3.14)$.

For a particle moving to the right, described by $\exp(ipx)$, there should be two reflection scenarios:

$$A. \exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad B \exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx) \quad ((3))$$

These are two physical situations, but one cannot distinguish between the two:

$$\exp(ipx) = .5 (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) + .5 (i) (1/i) (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)) \quad ((4))$$

We use i to separate the two physical scenarios, but then consider $\exp(ipx)$ as having a real and imaginary part

Thus $\exp(ipx)$ which only describes forwards motion is composed of two different physical dimensions describing p and reflection $-p$ with different phases for $-p$.

Deducing $P_1(px)$ from the Notion of Reflection and Periodicity

If one suggests that $P_1(px)$ is a periodic function in order that it not grow or shrink indefinitely and that the constraint L introduces the two physical conditions of $P_1(px)$ and $P_1(-px)$ for a reflected particle with phases -1 and $+1$ because of a crest trough situation, then it seems that one may deduce the form $\exp(ipx)$ from this condition i.e.

$$P_1(px) = .5 (P_1(px) + P_1(-px)) - .5 (P_1(px) - P_1(-px)) \quad ((5))$$

Thus: $P_1 \text{ real } (px) = .5 P_1(\text{real } (px)) + .5 P_1(\text{real } (-px))$ so $P_1 \text{ real}$ is even in px and periodic

Similarly $P_1 \text{ imaginary } (px)$ is odd in px .

Furthermore $P_1(px)P_1(-px) = 1$ so $P_1 \text{ real } (px)P_1(\text{real}(px)) + P_1 \text{ imaginary}(px)P_1 \text{ imaginary}(px) = 1$.

This leads to $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ as a possible solution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that by trying to describe a free particle in terms of probability in space, one needs to introduce the idea of a fixed length L in order to have normalization. In particular, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, but this applies to stationary particles, so $P_1(px)P_1(-px) = P(x)$ seems to apply, leading to $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ for $P_1(px)$. The form px is used for reasons described in Part I.

As a result, a free particle is associated with a constraint of L which physically seems to imply a particle and its reflection, i.e. p and - p together. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is periodic and has a wavelength of \hbar/p , the basic unit is half a wavelength, but this is associated with +1 for a crest and -1 for a trough. Thus, a free particle with reflection may consist of two pieces $\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)$. These are indistinguishable and so may be added together to give $\exp(ipx)$ in the following way:

$$\exp(ipx) = .5 (\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)) + .5 i (1/i) (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)) .$$

Thus, a free particle is actually associated with both p and -p due to reflection associated with a length constraint. This, we argue, explains the form $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ where both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ seem to imply interference of different p values.